

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 6/30/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N2/E1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.66	Bottom: 10.61
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:		Width: * 33-34 cm ?	Length: * 45 ?	Depth: 6 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
①	Sand	Grey	Packed	Fine	T ○	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
②	Gypsum Sand mix	Yellow to off white ★	Very Hard Packed	Rubbly	T 1 very Tiny FRAG	Lm ✓ Frags Throat	Gp
						Gr	Char ✓ Flecks
						Do	Throughout
					D ○	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan:	Sections: of Combined 1:10 w Fd3 Fc14- 15- 16
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: * Observed by SL cable Line, NE corner only cleared.
 ★ White phases to yellow at top of locus.
 ① Mod form laying in SL cable Line
 BEDROCK BOTTOM shows slight rust-red trace coloration